

Study Of Indian Film's Failure At The Oscars

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Abstract: The Academy Awards, popularly known as the Oscars are the awards that are presented for the technical, creative and artistic merit in the movie industry annually. The elite awards are given across 24 categories involving the best film directors, producers, actors, technicians and others associated with the movie. It's a matter of great honour to win the award or even get a nomination. Every year, the Film Federation of India selects one released movie of that year to represent India at the Oscars and submit it to the International Feature Film Award Committee in Los Angeles, the body that chooses the five nominations per category for the much desired film award in the global cinema. India makes around 2000 movies per annum, which is almost half of the total movies made around the world. In spite of being the highest producer of films in the world, no Indian movie have yet won the much coveted award. Using case studies, news reports and literature reviews, this paper will objectively study the selection procedure for the submission, its history, disappointments and the reasons of the failure of Indian cinema at the Oscars. This paper focusses on how the role of issues like plagiarisms, monetary problems and other critical reasons heavily impact the chances of Indian movies getting shortlisted at the world's biggest awards ceremony.

Index Terms - Oscars, Academy Award, Indian Film, Cinema, Feature Film, Movies, International Feature Film

I. INTRODUCTION

'Gandhi', 'Slumdog Millionaire' and 'Life of Pi' in which Indians won Oscars, were actually perceived, produced and directed by Non-Indians and most of us celebrated as if this was kind of victory for Indian Movie Industry, but actually none of these were completely Indian Movies. Only five Indians have won Oscars so far, Bhanu Athaiya, Resul Pookutty, AR Rahman, Gulzar & Satyajit Ray. Ray received honorary award in 1991 and all others have worked in the movies made by foreign production houses and filmmakers. In 1957, India for the first time sent a movie named 'Mother India' for the Oscars and it was nominated in the final five, but couldn't get the Academy's Best Foreign Language Film award. The other two films which were nominated in the final five were 'Salam Bombay!' in 1988 and 'Lagaan' in 2001. But none of these films have won the award. It was a very proud moment for us when the Indian documentary 'Writing with Fire' was selected in the Best Documentary Feature category in the Oscars 2022, but it lost to 'Summer of Soul (Or, When the Revolution Could Not Be Televised)' at the 94th edition of the Oscars. The Oscars are primarily intended for Hollywood films or English Language films. Out of 24 categories, Indian films or foreign language films can enter only one category i.e., Best International Feature Film. Without any surprise the films around the world compete with the submitted Indian film and every non-English country pushes their films in this category. It is also notable that 'Parasite' (Korean Movie) won 4 Oscars in 2020, Best Picture (for the production company), Best Director (individual), Best Original Screenplay (individual). But as a film, it had been nominated in just one category in which it won the — Best International Feature Film. It is not for the scarcity of talent that Indian movies do not get Oscars. The Indian film producers spend lavishly on sets, actors and songs but no brains are used for making a gripping storyline. Indian movie industry do not make films for the Western audience. They make films for the Indian audience. Indian films has its own characteristics with songs and dances that many thinks illogical for the global audience. But thanks to our huge population, our film industry can easily succeed catering to the Indian taste in terms of business.

II. REASONS FOR INDIAN FILM'S MEDIOCRE PERFORMANCE AT THE OSCARS

Bureaucracy: While doing research for this paper it has been found that many gems from India have simply not been able to get entry in the International Feature Film Category List. Every year the Oscars invite every nation to submit an official entry to their list. In India, Bureaucracy kicks in. The decision makers who decide which picture to send are usually utter failures as film directors or producers who consider themselves as 'Movie Critics'. A single call from a famous producer would make their decision easier. They give a priority berth to Bollywood films while ignoring regional language films unless some Bollywood Big Shot recommends the movie. In 2005, Red Chillies Productions twisted arms to ensure that their movie 'Paheli' was India's official entry over a Bengali film and a Malayali Film that were far better films. In 1998 the movie 'Jeans' was nominated as India's official entry which resulted in one committee member asking "Are they off their heads or do they think this is a Joke?"

Monetary Issue: An official entry is not enough. A movie nominated to a category must be projected across a number of film festivals. For International Feature Film Nominations, the Oscars require a minimum of 15 Shows across film festivals and each such show costs huge money. Suppose, if there is a rare movie that somehow gets nominated through its quality rather than its connections, it usually runs the required minimum of 15 shows and then it can't continue due to fund crisis. For example, an average show costs \$2000 and 15 shows mean \$30000 at least. Typically, many international films run for 50, 60 even 100 shows which increases its chances but Indian films which have the money for shows are of low quality, whereas good films do not have the money. A Marathi movie, 'Shwaas' was India's official entry for Best Foreign Language Film in the Oscars, 2004. But the team could not spend money of more than 14 shows and faced financial problems to exhibit and promote their film at the Oscars. Amitabh Bachchan donated Rs. 1 Lakh for the movie, while Govt. of Goa contributed 21 lakh and Govt. of Maharashtra gave 15 lakh rupees. The movie ran 14 shows during the Pre-Oscar bid and narrowly made out of the final five (Score 755.4, Next Best was 771). Had the movie got 50 shows - it would have got a slot in the nominations and could have the chance of winning.

Plagiarism: A shocking statistic is that out of 57 Indian films officially sent to the Oscars, 21 have been rejected due to plagiarism allegations (story is copied or familiar to already existing stories which naturally brings down the score). This blame is nothing new. Today's filmmakers are master copycats and rarely create anything original. As a result, many of our entries are marked with plagiarism and many films get low scores due to this factor. 'Barfi', 'Ek Lavanya', 'Heena' were some pictures which did not make the nominations because of possible plagiarism allegations.

Politics: Like in every other field in India, politics plays a huge role in this category. Somehow movie subjects related to India-Pakistan conflict or Indian freedom movement are always sent to the Oscars even though they are horribly bad over other high-quality movies. In 1999, A Mohanlal movie (Where he played a dancer) called 'Vanaprastham' was the best suited to be nominated but politics played a part and they submitted a movie called '1947: Earth' which ended up in dis-qualification. Preferences are always given to the Bollywood Movies over Bengali, Marathi, Malayali and other regional movies. Jeetu Joseph's 'Drishyam' was not submitted because the Govt officials believed that the film sent a wrong message that someone who outsmarted the system of law and order eventually wins.

III. CONCLUSION

From the above discussions and points it is understood why Indian movies never achieves anything in the Oscars. Bureaucracy, monetary problems, politics and plagiarism. It rears its ugly head everywhere. The need to change or alter the attitude of filmmaking and selection procedure can greatly benefit the Indian movie industry and can bring global recognitions and accolades. Filmmaking is an art that represents all arts and should be made with all seriousness to tell entertaining visual stories. Though in recent years movies are commercial in nature which are purely made to attract audiences and collect revenues, with power packed gimmicks, marketing and item songs, still in the last couple of years the rise of OTT (Over The Top) platforms have given a ray of hope to many young and small directors who have the potential to deliver great works. It will be good if the prominent film directors and producers come out of their comfort zone and experiment with some new ideas and strictly avoid the repetitive movies with the same plot. However more ethical discussions, debates and researches needs to be done to find the way for success of Indian films at the Oscars. Hopefully Indian films do things right and get rewarded in near future.

IV. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I thank my colleague and dear friend, Dr. Jyotirmay Deb of Techno India University for his comments and suggestions that greatly improved the manuscript.

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